

Green rice leafhopper resistance to malathion, methyl parathion, carbaryl, permethrin, and fenvalerate in Taiwan

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Green rice leafhoppers were collected from 10 sites throughout Taiwan in 1980. To measure susceptibility to the insecticides malathion, methyl parathion, carbaryl, permethrin, and fenvalerate, females were topically treated with the insecticide according to the FAO recommended method for the detection and measurement of insecticide resistance.

All populations showed various levels of resistance to malathion and methyl parathion (see table). Resistance ratios, as compared with data reported for the

Susceptibility to malathion, methyl parathion, carbaryl, permethrin, and fenvalerate of green rice leafhoppers in Taiwan.

Site	Resistance ratio ^a				
	Malathion	Methyl parathion	Carbaryl	Permethrin	Fenvalerate
I-lan	30	90	14	1.7	1.0
Hsin-chu	27	32	12	1.0	1.4
Dah4	250	226	79	5.5	1.0
Tsao-tung	408	235	74	2.1	1.4
Pai-ping	106	298	77	1.9	1.6
Pei-tung	288	326	37	4.9	1.9
Lu-ku	38	151	—	1.1	—
Chang-hua	225	172	47	2.9	2.3
Mei-nung	451	875	78	2.9	2.0
Ping-tung	368	554	24	2.2	1.5
Susceptible ^b strain	1	1	1	—	2.4

^aResistance ratio = LD₅₀ of each strain divided by LD₅₀ of susceptible or pertinent strain. ^bLD₅₀'s of malathion, methyl parathion, carbaryl, and fenvalerate against the susceptible strain were 0.57, 5.7, 0.71, and 0.34 µg/g, respectively. LD₅₀ of permethrin against Hsin-chu strain was 0.17 µg/g.

susceptible strain, ranged from 27 to more than 800. Resistance levels to carbaryl in these populations were somewhat lower, ranging between 12 and 79.

Permethrin and fenvalerate, two major synthetic pyrethroids recommended in 1980 for the control of this leafhopper, possessed higher inherent

toxicity to green rice leafhopper than the three conventional insecticides. Little, if any, resistance to the two synthetic pyrethroids was detected in the 10 multiresistant field populations, indicating no cross resistance between organophosphorus or carbamate compounds and synthetic pyrethroids. ■

Brown planthopper resistance to several insecticides in Taiwan

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The susceptibility to malathion, methyl parathion, MIPC, propoxur, permethrin, and fenvalerate of one susceptible (S), one malathion-resistant (R-mal), one MIPC-resistant (R-mipc), and four field strains of brown planthopper (BPH) from Taiwan was determined.

The 4th and 5th instars were sprayed with an acetone solution of insecticide. Toxicity of malathion, methyl parathion, and MIPC to the S strain was much lower than that of propoxur, permethrin, and fenvalerate (see table). The R-mal strain possessed some resistance to methyl parathion and MIPC. The R-mipc strain also showed some resistance to malathion and methyl parathion. Both R strains were significantly resistant to propoxur and permethrin, while remaining susceptible to fenvalerate. Field strains of BPH from heavily treated areas showed similar patterns of resistance to the six chemicals.

Susceptibility to 6 insecticides of 1 susceptible (S), 1 malathion-resistant (R-mal), 1 MIPC-resistant (R-mipc), and 4 field strains of brown planthopper in Taiwan.

Insecticide	LC ₅₀ (mg/ml) S	RR ^a					
		R-mal	R-mipc	Ping-tung	Mei-nung	Chia-yi	Tai-chung
Malathion	0.023	1183	574	526	359	437	288
Methyl parathion	0.029	82	44	41	48	84	32
MIPC	0.021	22	41	14	15	18	10
Propoxur	0.0067	72	76	36	46	36	19
Permethrin	0.0058	171	122	74	121	83	71
Fenvalerate	0.0083	5	5	1.6	2.9	3.0	1.7

^aResistance ratio = LC₅₀ of each strain divided by LC₅₀ of S strain.

Field populations of BPH could not have been previously exposed to synthetic pyrethroids; therefore, the permethrin resistance detected must represent cross-resistance from insecticides used previously. These include organochlorine, organophosphorus, and carbamate

compounds. Susceptibility of all strains to another synthetic pyrethroid fenvalerate could be taken as an indication that in the BPH permethrin might have a mode of action or metabolic fate different from that of fenvalerate. ■

Acetylcholinesterase sensitivity and carbamate resistance in brown planthopper

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The sensitivity of acetylcholinesterases (AChE) of susceptible (S) and MIPC-resistant (R) strains of brown plant-

hopper to MIPC and several other carbamate insecticides was determined. The homogenate of 4th and 5th instars was incubated with a series of concentrations of insecticide solution. Residual activity of AChE was measured using acetylthiocholine iodide as substrate.

AChE of the R strain was 15.7-times less sensitive to MIPC than the S strain (see table). The R strain AChE also was